

THE EFFECT OF YOU TUBE AND SONGS IN TEACHING VOCABULARY TO YOUNG LEARNERS.

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Abstract: *Vocabulary is considered to be exceedingly important by language learners , as without words, they cannot express their opinions freely. To comprehend and speak in English students must know about 2,000 word families. As teaching vocabulary is difficult to teach, teachers should be patient and search new ways of teaching vocabulary. One of the ways helping students to learn new words can be You Tube and songs from You tube. You Tube is social website where you can find videos in different themes, movies, presentations and other types of information. You Tube can be used in educational purposes to teach students vocabulary, utilizing with funny songs for children. This review provides information about teaching youngsters through You Tube songs, depending on literature review.*

Keywords; *vocabulary, songs, You Tube.*

Introduction Because English is the most extensively used communication tool in many nations and is sometimes referred to be an international language, we must study it. Listening, speaking, reading, and writing are the four key abilities that must be acquired when studying English. Students require English vocabulary to help them with these abilities, and they will be able to communicate in both spoken and written English if they have a large vocabulary (Hariyono,2020). Vocabulary offers an important foundation for students in conducting foreign language learning linked to vocabulary for young learners, the instructor must give innovative and engaging learning for students by utilizing the media tool Youtube so that kids are not bored (Sayidin, 2021). As our study habits and daily routines have altered tremendously, since the internet has proliferated. For instance, after waking up in the morning, activities such as checking news and messages from friends and family are common (Saban, 2019). Children also love playing mobile phones and computers with great pleasure, as it became common among young learners. Because of the drastic increase in using technologies, children's needs are

changed, they try to be virtually active at the moment. If they want to be online teachers also should try teach them online. Through mobile applications, online teaching English platforms, digital games and so on. In this article I want to provide with the teaching methods using YouTube videos and songs efficiently to the teachers of young learners. Firstly, what is YouTube? Youtube, according to Sianipar (2013), is a database that contains popular video material on social media, gives a wide range of highly useful information. Saban notes down that one of the social media technologies that has become a part of our life is YouTube. It is utilized as an instructional tool by many instructors(2019). Youtube has had a significant impact on all aspects of the information learning process for pupils, since the use of YouTube material has resulted in an internet-based knowledge base for today's millennials. Youtube is intended to be an information system, yet it has both positive and harmful consequences(Sayidin,2020). YouTube is a website, where we can find all information about different issues. According to the research of Saban YouTube has been most frequently identified with a technology tool. YouTube is referred to as "everything" in the reasons section. YouTube is frequently used by students. More people watch YouTube channels about daily life, online games, and entertainment. YouTube will be used for instructional reasons by the participants. Few students aspire to be YouTube celebrities. Teachers and schools must be able to create activities that make effective use of YouTube in a pedagogical setting (2019).

Furthermore, English songs are also another tool for instructors to teach new words effectively. Music is universal in a way that words cannot express. A sensation is created by the rhythm. The lyrics are examples of the vocabulary used in the song. As a result, songs are valuable resources in language courses. Learners become more willing to learn as a result of the rhythm and melody. Music It holds their attention and aids in the memorization of the words(Akyuz, Yavuz,2017). Duisembekova explains the importance of songs as frequently used in educational settings. Consider learning to read as a first step. Learning the letters of the alphabet is a common first step for beginning readers. Could a song aid in remembering the letters' order? The majority of native English speakers would say yes. The 26 letters of the alphabet have been sung countless times to help children learn the alphabet to the tune of "Twinkle, Twinkle, Little Star." When a student listens to a song, they feel emotion and a sense of connection, which can serve as a bridge to acquiring the specific abilities they require. (2022).

Literature reviewThe role of vocabulary in young learners.

English is the most extensively used language for international communication around the world, and many countries, including the United States, Singapore, and Australia, have designated English their official language. It is necessary to master English vocabulary(Sayidin.2021).

According to Harmer in Kurniawati (2011,cited in Sayidin,2021), vocabulary is one feature of English. It is critical for pupils to have a strong vocabulary. Students who solely learn grammar will struggle if they are not already accustomed to grasping vocabulary. "Vocabulary can be characterized, basically, as the words we teach in the foreign language," write Syafrizal and Haerudin (2018,cited in Hariyano,2020). A new item of 42 vocabulary, on the other hand, could be more than a single word: for example, post office and mother-in-law, which are made up of two or three words yet represent the same notion."

Young learners are those who are between the ages of 5 and 12. Teachers must be aware that young kids have a hard time distinguishing between the real and imaginary worlds. However vocabulary is essential for students youngsters have difficulties with understanding of role vocabulary so that teachers should use new, innovative ways of teaching them.

You tube in teaching vocabulary. YouTube is the second most popular social media platform behind Facebook, with approximately 1.9 billion members globally (www.wearesocial.com, 2019). YouTube is a social media platform where users may upload and share videos. YouTube's mission statement is "to give everyone a voice and a chance to learn about the world" (YouTube, 2019). Google owns YouTube, which is used by millions of people every day. The majority of the films are for enjoyment, but there is also instructive content (Fleck, Beckman, Sterns, & Hussey, 2014, cited in Saban, 2019).

YouTube allows users to publish and view videos, as well as connect with other users, in its most basic form (ozkonuk, 2019,cited in Saban,2019). Within video sharing services, users can establish their own channels and arrange video lists by modifying these channels. Users who have the ability to remark on published videos can do so on the videos they view or post.

Furthermore, youtube is the site where students have an open access to different lessons of native teachers from all parts of the world and have master trainings, videos, movies, motivating clips and so on. Using you tube is very convenient, you can watch lessons or videos at any time and anywhere you want.

Hariyono focused on how students are involved in teaching vocabulary using videos on YouTube. The findings are presented in two themes: student responses to classroom activities and teacher instructions and student involvement in the use

of YouTube. It was discovered that students respond positively to teaching and learning activities, that young learners interact with the teacher and other students, that they are ready to ask questions, and that they use videos. It is easier for pupils to understand terminology when they watch videos on YouTube. English teachers should be creative and able to vary their technique in teaching language through video, researchers suggest.

English songs in teaching vocabulary to young learners.

Young students like engaging in things that make them feel good. In order to read, spell, and write vocabulary, students must be motivated to learn and memorize vocabulary items. Students' motivation will be boosted in an interesting way, such as through the use of music. Continuously listening to English songs might be an alternate strategy to begin a new habit of learning new language. This strategy is not only entertaining, but it is also one of the most effective ways to introduce new language(Duisembekova,2014).In vocabulary instruction, a variety of strategies might be described. Music is universal in a way that words cannot express. A sensation is created by the rhythm. The lyrics are examples of the vocabulary used in the song. As a result, songs are valuable resources in language courses. Learners become more willing to learn as a result of the rhythm and melody. Music holds their attention and aids in word memorization (Akyuz & Yavuz, 2017).

Unconsciously, song might speed up the language acquisition process by assisting students in pronouncing and reading words rapidly. Children require appropriate music to sing, such as joyful songs, pleasant songs, busy songs, and amusing songs. There are many things that can be taught to young children through songs that they will remember for the rest of their lives, and there are songs about most basic concepts like letters, numbers, colors, weekdays, months, seasons, body parts, and clothes that will make the lessons come alive and exciting. Furthermore, songs are crucial teaching tools for establishing a comfortable and natural classroom ethos, and so may be beneficial in overcoming emotions of shyness and hesitancy on the side of the students. Students can be introduced to a range of new terminology through songs. Do you want to help your students improve their vocabulary by teaching them valuable phrases, words, and expressions? Songs are nearly typically written for native speakers, hence they usually include current language, idioms, and expressions (Duisembekova,2014).

The study was done by Duisembekova on the effect of songs on children demonstrated that the experimental group's vocabulary competence improved significantly more than the control group's. According to the findings, YouTube can

help people learn new terms more effectively. YouTube might be incorporated into an English course, according to one suggestion. The class benefited from this procedure in a variety of ways. During the trial, the classroom climate was substantially better than when the typical activities were implemented. The students were more interested in the class and focused on the lyrics in order to pick up new terminology(2014).

ConclusionIt is unrefutable fact that learning A language cannot be completed without vocabulary learning. To meet the need of children in 21st century it is essential for teachers to engage students to learn through social websites, as children are keen on being virtually active. Youtube and english songs influence was discussed in this review, to sum up you tube is considered to be very comfortable and open access with many video-lessons for teachers to use, while teaching young learners. Additionally, songs also have unchangeable place in our life. For instructors and students, incorporating the usage of YouTube videos and songs in foreign languages is a wonderful resource. To collect the relevant data for this review, Google scholars and ERIC websites were used.

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